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Scrumban learning – agile, lean and transparent framework for practical learning experience

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ABSTRACT

Large, mid-large and/or wide practical work is important part of engineering education in almost any development field. In the practical work, student groups innovate, plan and implement usually large outcome. Because of teamwork and often-complex topic, creation of the outcome is challenging for students. Furthermore, often teachers have limited visibility to practical work itself, its phases and related progression in group or student level. Based on our study and experience we have created new framework for practical learning experience called Scrumban learning. It is compilation of two development frameworks; Scrum and Kanban. In this paper, we introduce a new detailed framework for practical work development in the engineering education. The created learning framework has following main dimensions; iterative design methodology based on a cyclic process of creation of practical work outcome, incremental model where the outcome is innovated, planned and implemented incrementally until the desired outcome is finished and creation of visualisation, where students, group and teachers are able to see student level tasks, plan for development and progression of work. We have tested the practical work framework with more than 110 practical works and 450 students during one academic year in two implementations of same engineering course. Benefits of the framework are clear and furthermore, three set targets for iterative and visualized practical work with room for formative assessment have been achieved. Study results presented in this paper are useful for any engineering learning organization to create and implement their practical work establishment based on this Scrumban learning framework.

1 INTRODUCTION

Practical works are important part of engineering education in almost any development field. In practical work, student groups innovate, plan and implement usually quite large outcomes, which can be anything from design documentations to solution implementations. With mid-large to large and/or wide practical work, managing the execution of the practical work introduces challenges for both students and teachers.

Challenges from the students' point of view include team management and producing suitable outcome for the practical work. Students may work in groups with previously unknown students so team management may include; defining motivational goals, establishing ways of communication, ways to divide responsibilities and ways to make sure each group member completes their responsibilities. To produce acceptable outcome, students must be able to estimate the time required to complete the work so they reserve enough time for work, to identify complex areas, and to follow which parts are completed and which require more work.

Challenges for teachers are related to observing and supporting the groups during their working phase. If teachers have limited visibility to the progression of the groups and involvement of individual students, teacher cannot offer support to groups that are falling behind and problems during practical work surface only when it is too late.

To manage the challenges, we present a concept of Scrumban learning: a framework that combines Agile and Lean methods to iterative process to support the practical work advancement. Teachers provide the backlog of items that must be completed to finish the practical work, but student groups are responsible for deciding how the backlog items are divided into more manageable tasks and how the work is allocated between students. Students are instructed to work in Sprints between the deadlines and the iterative process supports continuous feedback and formative evaluation.

Each student group maintains a Kanban board, which supports the students' team management but also offers window for teachers to see how students are dividing their tasks, how much of the work they have completed and if there are clear discrepancies with participation between students.

The framework was tested on two consecutive course implementations with over 450 students and 110 groups in total. Feedback data from students was collected from dedicated survey made for students in the latter course. Teacher feedback was collected with group discussion session.

The paper is structured as follows: Chapter two discusses the concepts of Agile and Lean and describes the Scrumban method, and related work. In Chapter three we present the Scrumban learning framework and discuss the experiences gained from using it with practical work during software engineering course, from both teacher and student perspective. Chapter four summarizes the work.

2 AGILE AND LEAN APPROACHES

2.1 Agile concepts

Use of Agile methods and iterative model has been continuing to increase in engineering education. Today it is increasingly used, mostly in software engineering industry, but in other fields as well. The Agile Method is a special approach to project management that is utilized today in many industry areas. This method assists groups in responding to the unpredictability of constructing products and uses incremental, iterative work cycles that are called Sprints. The Sprint is a period of time allocated for

a special implementation phase of a project. During the time period Sprints are planned to be complete and there will be no more work on that certain phase of the project. These development cycles continue until the remaining phases of the project are implemented or the product developed is ready enough. Agile methods focus on the following main principles; people, individuals and interactions over processes and systems, implement rather than document, outline plans over detailed specifications and customer collaboration over contract negotiation. [1]

Scrum is the main and mostly used method in Agile principles family. Scrum has key roles, ceremonies and artifacts. Main roles are Product owner, Scrum master and a Scrum Team. Ceremonies are Sprint planning, Sprint review, retrospective and daily scrum meeting. Artifacts are Product Backlog, Sprint Backlog and an increment of potentially shippable version of the product. The product owner creates a prioritised list of product features (Product Backlog) to be implemented. The Product Backlog is changing during the development of product and product owner should refine and modify it when needed. In the Sprint planning a team, Scrum master (facilitator) and product owner (if necessary) break down the selected few items from Product Backlog to be implemented in coming Sprint and list of those tasks is called Sprint Backlog. During the Sprint team is implementing tasks from that prioritised Sprint Backlog. In Scrum method team is having daily Scrum meeting to follow the progress and there team members are telling what they have achieved, what they are doing next and then discuss if there are any challenges, issues and help needed. At the end of Sprint, all planned work should be completed and Sprint review meeting is held to inspect implemented features and unfinished tasks. Usually product owner facilitates this meeting and together with customer accepts or rejects the work done. Last ceremony of Scrum method in every development cycle (iteration) is retrospective where team will discuss how they have been performing and is there anything to be changed in their daily work in name of continuous improvement. [1]

The use of Agile methods in education, starting from its origin, has so far been focused to software engineering education, but is increasingly coming to other education fields of engineering. When using Agile methods in software engineering education [2] it is also helping students to learn about modern software engineering processes [3]. When applying Agile methods in larger scale in the engineering field it has included changes in teaching approaches [4] and supporting teamwork [5]. Scrum is an iterative process framework for Agile development and can be used in education field. It provides a useful framework, where learning can take a place e.g. in area of practical works inside engineering courses. In education field, it is framework which has been successfully applied in schools as one way to give better and transparent control over students' learning [6]. [7]

2.2 Lean concepts

Lean development is the focusing on Lean principles in product development. Lean got its start in manufacturing, as a way to optimize the production line to minimize waste and maximize value to the customer. These two principles are relevant to any product development. It is also focusing to follow a repeatable process and requires special quality standards. Furthermore, it relies on the collaboration of a group of professional workers in order to get the work done. Applying Lean principles to any knowledge work requires a shift in mind-set, in terms of how waste, value, and other key Lean concepts are already defined. Lean has seven principles for development;

eliminate waste, build quality in, create knowledge, adapt to commitment, deliver fast, respect people, and optimize the whole development. [8]

Kanban is one of the Lean principle implementation methods. It has roots as a scheduling tool developed by Toyota for Lean production of car industry to help improve production and inventory control. As Kanban means “visual card” in Japanese, it helps making scheduling more visual and helps support Just-In-Time (JIT) manufacturing. Furthermore, it helps reducing flow times within production and response times from suppliers and to customers [9]. Kanban board is good tool to visualise the workflow by using cards progress through specified columns in the board. Those columns can be named simply e.g. “Todo”, “Doing” and “Done”. This visualisation is useful for every stakeholder the development project has. Kanban board has a Work In Progress (WIP) limit, which means that there is a limit how many tasks can be in “Doing” at the same time. Kanban boards are widely used management tools. A task board allowing evaluation and further planning (break down) of the development project and furthermore, also being able to keep customer and other stakeholders informed the changing status of the product development.

In education field, when using e.g. practical works as part of engineering course, task board, like Kanban board, provide efficient visualisation tool for tracking student groups with status updates. It keeps every stakeholder of the course up-to-date how work is proceeding and can be physical (classroom whiteboard) or virtual board (e.g. Trello tool) having a working area divided to different columns presented already.

2.3 Scrumban

The similarities between the two methodologies (Scrum and Kanban), on one hand use transparency to improve processes and differentiating aspects on the other hand. Since Kanban is not a process method, it is typically used in conjunction with some other method. As Scrum has been a popular selection, Scrum and Kanban are brought together formally in Scrumban [10]. With Scrum the amount of development work that is ongoing is limited by the Sprint time box, but in Scrumban there are no time-limited Sprints, so the development team must make limitation itself through the use of WIP limits on the board [7]. This is how Scrumban was born – approach in software development that calls on technical and methodological compromises between these parent methodologies [11]. In engineering education Scrumban is very useful method with good collection of principles and way of work inherited from its parent processes. Scrumban can be seen as a useful process for e.g. practical work in the engineering courses. Later in this paper we present Scrumban as a learning framework for engineering courses and feedback from our experiences from use of it.

2.4 Related work

The concept of design and using Agile as an approach to engineering education is not a new idea [e.g. 12]. There is a rich collection of different articles providing information about research and practical approaches for both teaching Agile (“the what”) and using Agile as a pedagogical approach (“the how”) [12]. This fundamental difference between approaches can be seen among research papers. Our target was to create framework for using Agile method(s) as teaching framework. Dewi and Muniandy [13] have created quite large-scale literature review for contribution of the Agile methodology towards teaching and learning finding answers to research question, among others, what are the suggested Agile related approaches and methods used to improve teaching and learning. There are also some research papers for overall Agile learning principles [e.g. 14], saying Agile learning applies the processes and principles of Agile

software development to context of learning. Gary et. al. [15] have approached from different angle and published a platform for applying Agile principles for learning evaluation and creating formative feedback for students.

Research of certain Agile method or methods have also been published during last decade. Royle and Nikolie [1] introduces pedagogical method delivered from Agile work practices, particularly the Scrum method of project based learning. Also Cobric's [16] paper is to describe, evaluate and discuss a method for teaching Agile project management and Agile is not only a subject domain in that paper, also teaching method itself is based on Scrum. Sharp and Lang [12] present in their paper both Agile methods, XP and Scrum, related articles on the area of Agile teaching and learning. Also Alfonso and Botia [17] presents use of an iterative and Agile process model with Scrum and XP features to serve both as an educational technique (for teachers) and as a subject of learning (for students) in the area of software engineering. D'Souza and Rodrigues propose in their paper "Extreme Pedagogy, a student-centred teaching-learning conceptual framework to have higher quality in engineering education" [18]. Extreme Pedagogy aims at continuous improvement of student learning, trying to keep students' needs and satisfaction as its focus.

In the area of Lean and Agile education Parsons et. al. [7] presented Scrum and Kanban methods and specially usage of Trello as virtual tool for an approach in combined Agile and Lean methods. Noguera et. al. [19] presented methodologies from other fields to be incorporated to enrich their educational model and they were especially interested in Agile and Lean methodologies. As a result of a literature review, a pilot test to implement Agile learning in virtual contexts was proposed. Taking into account the benefits of the Agile method for teamwork, Noguera et.al. [20] analysed the usefulness of Agile strategies (like Scrum and Kanban) for team regulation and project management in online higher education. Kanban as part of education approach can be found from papers Ovais et. al. [21] as part of Software Factory related education and Bacea et. al. [22] for teaching Agile product development processes to provide centralised team tracking with frequent task status updates.

3 SCRUMBAN LEARNING

3.1 Scrumban learning framework

Our concept for practical work framework in education is called Scrumban learning. It is based on Software Engineering Scrumban method, which is collaboration of special features from Agile Scrum management method and Lean Kanban method. *Fig. 1* presents our Scrumban learning framework.

Fig. 1. Scrumban learning framework

As a first action, in our framework, teacher creates practical work backlog for students to implement. Backlog items can be divided based on the subject and usually are divided based on subject related features, incremental add-ons for selected core knowledge of the subject or iterative working implementations of the subject. Our framework consists also middle and final presentations and deliveries which are examples and not necessarily needed in every practical work implementation in engineering education. Before student can start the implementation, teacher can guide students to Scrumban framework and content of practical work. Furthermore, Kanban board (virtual or physical) and first column (“Todo”) for it needs to be created.

Overall plan how many Sprints for given course schedule needs to be created by the group of students, considering implementation of whole practical work with possible milestones. Before first iterative implementation Sprint starts, student group (4-8 students) selects first set of items from practical work backlog which they planned to implement in first increment (Sprint). Then they need to break down those items to smaller pieces (tasks) and plan who is responsible and what will be an estimation of workload (week/days/hours) for each of those tasks. Result of that planning is Sprint Backlog of first Sprint and needs to be published in Kanban board as content column e.g. “Next Sprint”.

When implementation of first tasks begins, those “task cards” in Kanban board will be moved to next column “Doing”. While Implementation (Sprint) is ongoing the group cannot be disturbed by other stakeholders. Group will have regular meetings (e.g. weekly) to present their doings and possible problems to other group members. When all tasks planned for Sprint are implemented, it is time for Sprint review. Sprint review can be done by the group, group with teacher/course assistant, group with other student group or all stakeholders together. In the review group presents the planned work done and not done. There is also room for feedback and peer evaluation as guidance and part of formative assessment of the course. After each Sprint in Kanban

board all implemented “task cards” need to be moved to third column “Done”. Before group continues to plan for next Sprint, they need to discuss shortly their way of work in previous Sprint as part of continuous development (retrospective). These iterative and incremental implementation rounds (Sprints) continue until all items from practical work backlog has been implemented or deadline for practical work has been achieved and the latest reviewed outcome will be the final one.

This created framework has several improvements compared to traditional practical work implementation in engineering education where given topic for work is given in the beginning and numerical evaluation is in the end. From the students’ point of view iterative approach help students to split the work better for smaller manageable pieces, resource and schedule tasks in better level to divide work for the whole time period given for this kind of work. This framework also gives opportunity to better cooperation between students and increase collaboration in common tasks. Continuous improvement gives room for better results and positive learning curve for individual students. Furthermore, framework gives room for better communication and visualisation through used Kanban board.

From teacher point of view the framework gives room for better possibilities to observe groups’ working, as well as room for formative feedback and assessment options. Visualisation with Kanban board gives teachers better overview and it elucidates status of work while at the same time improves possibilities to guide groups in their process way of work. Teacher can also see individual students’ contribution to teamwork from Kanban cards. Teacher can implement several formative assessments e.g. peer feedback (group to group, or individual students to each other within a group), self-evaluations, review meetings for giving feedback to groups and continuous feedback via Kanban board for groups way of work.

3.2 Scrumban learning experiences

Our Scrumban framework has now been used at two Bachelor course implementations, namely two-period (14 weeks) and five credit units course Introduction to Software Engineering, first in Autumn 2018 and then in Spring 2019. More than 450 students and 110 groups implemented the practical work. In the beginning of practical work, students were introduced Agile methods and Kanban, and after that Scrumban framework used at our courses. Both courses had similar relatively large practical work for software system requirements phase, which was made in two phases; first a preliminary requirements documentation, and final requirements documentation.

In the end of both phases student group presentations were held and furthermore, there were room for peer-evaluations, self-evaluation, and teacher feedback. Evaluations were handled by Peer Review Program (PRP), a web application made at our university. The focus on middle presentations was in stakeholder analysis, and on requirements and diagrams on the final presentations. Course staff acted as a customer, while student group represented the software company.

Groups used Trello tool as Kanban board to plan, create and track their Sprint Backlogs (traditional Todo-Doing-Done), and some groups also put meetings and deadlines in cards at their own column. Teacher gave feedback to groups via own cards Trello at board. Most groups used to have weekly meetings during the Sprints.

Framework was tested with qualitative teacher discussion and quantitative survey and results were used as primary data. Students’ feedback about the Scrumban process

was collected on the latter course with separate, non-mandatory but bonus point giving survey. From the 166 students, 127 answered the survey. In the survey, students were asked to reflect on the usefulness of different aspects such as the Kanban board, iterative process and formative evaluation in the Scrumban learning framework.

When asked about the formative evaluation in the Scrumban process, 91% of students considered it better to receive feedback during the execution of the practical work rather than only afterwards. Only 6% of answerers felt that the process did not support giving feedback to students.

Fig. 2 shows the results of how positively students felt about the iterative process and dividing the work into smaller pieces. Students could choose as many of the options as they felt suitable. In the same question they could also pick if their group followed the iterative process actively (32 % of answerers picked that option), followed the iterative process moderately (picked by 61 %) or did not follow the process either by working in last moment or as a big chunk (picked by 9 %). It should be noted that some answerers did not pick any of the options regarding how their group followed the process and some picked more than one. Students felt positively about the iterative process and dividing the work into smaller pieces, even though some of them did not fully utilise it during this course.

Fig. 3 shows the results about how students viewed the usage of Kanban board in their practical work. Students could pick as many of the options as they wanted. Vast majority (90%) considered it helpful for visualizing the work.

Fig. 2. Iteration and dividing of work

Fig. 3. Kanban board support

Teacher feedback was collected in discussion session where the course staff from the both course implementations was present. Discussion focused on four topics: How did the teachers feel about the change from traditional practical work process, did the process improve options for evaluation and feedback, how did the Kanban board work from teacher's perspective and what kind of possibilities the visualisation offers, and would the teachers use the framework on other courses.

Teachers noted that the communication with students was more distributed over the course periods instead of focusing in the last days before the deadline as the students worked iteratively. In addition, the grading and evaluation work is more distributed over the course. This needs to be taken into account while planning the work load as it may not be possible to use the teaching intermissions for the grading and evaluation. On the other hand, as part of the grading can be done during the course, it lessens the workload after the final deadline as earlier parts are already evaluated, though on practical works where the integrity and consistency between different parts is a requirement for students, teachers might have to review the already graded parts again, increasing total workload slightly.

Teachers felt that evaluation has stronger basis when there is information available through the whole process and it is possible to guide the work towards better end result based on the partial deliveries. Framework also supports feedback from other sources than the teacher, peer reviews or stakeholder evaluations can be given from partial or final deliveries.

Using the Kanban board gave with relatively quick glance a good picture about how the group is progressing. Using tool that shows history in addition to the current situation allows teacher to periodically check the progression and work division between the groups. Also possible "free-rider" students in groups could be detected. However, if there are multiple groups that the teacher is overseeing, the amount of work will be non-negligible and should be again taken into account while planning suitable workload.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Created conceptual framework for practical works in engineering education is presented in this paper. Framework is based on combination of Agile method called Scrum and Lean method called Kanban. Framework is tested in engineering course with quite large practical work during two implementations of the course. More than 110 student groups have used the framework and in the end second implementation of the course additional feedback was collected and analysed. Goals for this Scrumban learning framework seems to be achieved. Feedback shows framework has been useful tool for practical works from students' and teachers' point of view. Main improvements for traditional practical work implementation are iterative approach for quite large and usually quite unknown subject of work, transparency through visualisation of ongoing work, visualisation of tasks and responsibilities, and dividing work both earlier and better during the time-box given and between team members of the student group. Teacher discussion also gave conclusion that framework works also for other fields of education, but needs understanding the ideas of related Agile and Lean principles and techniques. Furthermore, framework gives more opportunities for formative assessment and feedback, like teacher observation via visualised process, collaborative feedback between groups and students as well as self-evaluations. Trello

as a tool for Kanban board was used to track student groups' and group members' work process along the course. Trello is recommended for this kind of approaches, because of its ease of use, flexibility, and many useful features.

Research related Agile learning environments will continue to find even better solutions in the area of the engineering education. Will be seen how combination of other different principles from engineering field will be researched and experienced in the engineering education.

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